

Robust Autonomous Navigation of Vehicles using Visual Reinforcement Q-learning.

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Abstract—Recent advances in the manufacturing technology of vehicles has led to a dramatic increase in their production which in turn has led to the need of efficient and robust autonomous navigation systems. Since the model of the environment in which the vehicle will move is unknown, this makes the task very challenging. In this work we have developed an unsupervised visual reinforcement Q-learning based system for autonomous navigation of vehicles. Here we use the fact that Q-learning is able to learn even without a model of the environment. Q-learning approaches try to predict an action-value function that gives the expected utility of taking a given action in a given state and then following a fixed policy. The testing of the algorithm was done on different simulated environments using an open source simulator TORCS. The input video from vehicle camera is first preprocessed and then Edge detection is done. Then some strategically important regions are extracted from the image. The steering angle of the vehicle is predicted from the number of pixels in these strategic regions using Q-learning. Everything is done in real time which makes the proposed algorithm efficient. Simulation and experimental results show that the proposed algorithm can accurately, robustly and efficiently be used for autonomous navigation of vehicles in unknown environments.

Keywords-component: *Artificial Intelligence, Neural Networks, Computer Vision*

I. INTRODUCTION

Humans are easily able to perform the complex task of driving vehicles which involves analyzing complex visual scenes and then taking appropriate motor action in real time. The important question here is how are humans able to do this task so efficiently and in real time?

Neurological and cognitive studies such as [5] show that humans remove irrelevancies so that they can concentrate on only the important regions. Thus analyzing only certain regions in the visual video substantially reduces the complexity of visual operations. At the time of driving on a new unknown track they perform the required actions only by analyzing these important regions. In our work we use this top down process which filters out the important regions and then use Reinforcement Learning (Q-learning) to learn the action map for successful driving.

The open source racing simulator TORCS [2] was used for the experimentation. The analysis of visual scenes was done using OpenCV (Open Source Computer Vision) which is a library for real time image processing and computer vision. TORCS has various facilities like creating a virtual vehicle and controlling its various aspects like acceleration, steering angle, gear, break etc.

Based on visual perception many animated systems have already been developed e.g. system developed by Tu, X. and Terzopoulos, D. for animating a group of artificial fishes [3]. The fishes have limited field of view. These sensor-based approaches are effective in generating localized behavior information but this algorithm would become inefficient for real time mapping when there are many features in image.

TORCS was used to simulate the vehicle and the environment. The mapping between the relevant regions in visual frame and steering angle was learned using Q-Learning. The results obtained show that Q-Learning can be successfully applied to make the vehicle learn to navigate successfully by itself without knowing the track details in advance. Note that Q-learning is able to learn even without a model of the environment which gives us the inspiration to use it in this problem.

II. ALGORITHM

There are four important modules of our autonomous navigation system which have the following tasks:

1. Video acquisition and preprocessing module:

Its task is video acquisition from the vehicle camera and preprocessing it to remove noise. It is described in further detail in Section A.

2. Relevant region selector module:

Its task is to select the relevant regions in the frames of the video. Note that this relevant region selection which we propose is a novel strategy which is based on [5] and our finding in which we got the result that humans concentrate more on certain regions of the visual video while driving and ignore others. This greatly helps in reducing the time complexity of operations involved making the system real time. It is described in further detail in Section B.

3. Learning Module.

Its task is to find the steering angle of the vehicle in real time using the relevant regions such that proper navigation of the vehicle takes place. The mapping between the relevant regions and the steering angle is learnt in real time using Q-learning. It is described in further detail in Section C.

4. Driving the vehicle using the steering angle returned by the algorithm.

This task is concerned with mechanical engineering and is beyond the scope of this paper.

A. Video Acquisition and pre processing

The camera is assumed to be placed at the front of the vehicle and having good resolution. The open source library OpenCV is used for video processing. The frames are converted to grayscale and morphological operations like opening and closing are performed to remove noise from the frames. Then the frames are smoothened by a Gaussian function. The threshold limits are then specified to detect disturbances (edges) on sides of lane. Differentiation of the resulting image is then done to calculate the gradient values and extract the edges in the relevant regions. This method is a slightly modified version of the canny edge detector [6].

B. Selecting the relevant regions of the video.

The idea behind extracting relevant regions is that we need to concentrate at some relevant regions only. This can bring down a substantial reduction in the complexity of the overall task. Studies on attention have shown that these regions of interest depend on top-down attention. Top-down attention relies on the task as demonstrated in experiments such as change blindness [7]. Itti-Koch [8] gave a bottom up saliency model to predict gaze patterns. Peters and Itti [9] have given a mechanism for including top-down processes in their model. They create a task relevance saliency map based on low level image features and combine it with the Itti-Koch bottom up saliency model to predict gaze patterns. A study on Dynamic attention by Maji, Mukerjee and Singh [10] shows that that in dynamic scenes human attention is object driven and localized motion is a significant determiner of object conspicuity.

The extracting of features was done using affine invariant regions which were constructed by selecting areas from intensity watershed image segmentation. Areas which are approximately stationary as the intensity threshold is varied are selected as the regions of interest. These regions detected are taken as the key feature points for the image. The lane edges are detected sufficiently well by these regions. SIFT descriptor [11] was used for describing the key points as vectors. These descriptors are also robust to changes in illumination, noise, occlusion and minor changes in viewpoint. Also these SIFT descriptors give region description vectors which are invariant to affine transformations of the image.

Figure 1. Clustering results for $k=5$. The clusters are sufficiently descriptive as the lane edges are clustered as one cluster.

The SIFT descriptors obtained from the scene are cluttered to find the lane edges. Clustering is done over all the features across all the images in the training set. Kmeans clustering algorithm was used and Euclidean distance was used as the distance function. The number of clusters k was chosen to be five by experimental verification. Clustering results as can be seen from Figure 1 are sufficiently distinctive.

While driving one looks at some distance ahead and depending on the lane turns the steering in an appropriate manner. One does not look in the middle of the lane or its edges just ahead. The features which persist across the frames are the ones which help in making the decision to turn. So, we try to locate the regions where most such persisting features occur. Such regions will be the attention prior for this task.

SIFT features are used as in the previous step. Then using bag of words technique the regions are found out which are not changing between frames. Matching of different frames is done by determining the nearest neighbor (NN) using Euclidean distance as the distance measure. The features in adjacent frames which match are taken as the important regions for that scene. Finally the regions which are selected for the learning task are as shown in Figure 2.

C. Learning the steering angle from the relevant region pixels.

Given the relevant regions in the consecutive frames, the goal now is to learn the mapping between the pixels of relevant regions and the steering angle so that given an unknown frame we can extract the relevant regions and then using the mapping find the steering angle for proper navigation of the car. The mapping is learnt using Q-learning reinforcement technique.

III. LEARNING METHODOLOGY

Reinforcement Learning is an approach for an autonomous agent learning to choose optimal actions in order to achieve its goals by sensing and acting in its environment. This is also the basic learning process in the nature. For example, when children do something good then

Figure 2. Typical frames after preprocessing and edge detection. The four rectangles represent the relevant regions.

parents appreciate them and if they do something wrong then parent's criticize them and over a period of time the child learns how to live in a society as a good citizen. Thus the main idea of reinforcement learning is to find a relation between the cause and the effect. The reinforcement learning which we used is delayed Q-learning [4]. In this method random action maps are taken and after some time quality of state- action pair is computed using some reward function.

If rewards are high then that state-action pair is considered good and is chosen. Since Q-learning is able to learn even without a model of the environment it is particularly useful for our problem.

We define the following state-action pairs for the Q-learning: Let s_1 , s_2 be the two states and let a_1 , a_2 be the corresponding actions. Then (s_1, a_1) and (s_2, a_2) are the two state-action pairs.

Let s_1 be the sum of white pixels in the two highlighted windows towards left (red and green) or stated mathematically:

$$s_1 = \text{WhitePixels}(w_1) + \text{WhitePixels}(w_2). \quad (1)$$

w_1 = the number of white pixels in the smaller left window.

w_2 = the number of white pixels in the larger left window.

Similarly let s_2 be the sum of all pixels in two highlighted windows towards right (red and green) or stated mathematically:

$$s_2 = \text{WhitePixels}(w_3) + \text{WhitePixels}(w_4). \quad (2)$$

w_3 = the number of white pixels in the smaller right window.

w_4 = the number of white pixels in the larger right window.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

First of all, states (s_1 and s_2) are obtained from the video frames using Open CV library. Then these states (s_1 and s_2) are passes through Random action maps a_1 and a_2 . That is each time a random value of a_1 and a_2 is chosen and resultant is calculated. The resultant is given by:

$$\text{Resultant} = \{(a_1) * (s_1) + (a_2) * (s_2)\}. \quad (3)$$

The block diagram of the network is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The block diagram of neural network used for Q-learning.

An important observation at this point is that whenever the car goes towards left side of the lane, the disturbances in left windows increases and similarly for the right side of the lane the disturbances in right windows increases. After that car could be guided so that it remains on the lane. We exploit the above observation to guide the car. From the above observation we can intuitively say that a steering angle is a function of the resultant. Choosing the function to be linear we can say that:

$$\text{Steering angle} = k * \{(a_1) * (s_1) + (a_2) * (s_2)\}. \quad (4)$$

The State field can be considered as an input layer, the Action field as a hidden layer and the Resultant field as an output layer. Then the system can be trained using a Feed forward Neural Network [1]. The weights a_1 , a_2 are learnt from the Network.

From the resultant calculated by the network, the steering angle is obtained using (4) which is then used for driving the car. After some period of time rewards are calculated. An intuitive and logical measure of rewards which we have taken here is the distance of the vehicle from centre of the lane. Rewards are high when the vehicle is more in middle of the lane and less when it is near edges of lane. Now if rewards are sufficient then the corresponding mapping is accepted otherwise those mappings are rejected. After all above steps again whole process is repeated, that is passing through neural net above and then analyzing resultant. Finally the average of the actions from the accepted mappings is taken which are the learnt a_1 and a_2 .

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Five experiments were conducted on different tracks and the vehicle was made to learn. Table I shows the results of the accepted mappings ((state, action) pairs) in different experiments. Table II shows the error values obtained in the different experiments during the learning phase and after the first, second, third and fourth accepted mappings.

Figure 5 shows the graph of error versus the number of mappings taken. Clearly as it can be seen the graph is monotonically decreasing which proves the convergence of our approach.

The learning error decreases in almost all the experiments as the number of mappings taken is increased. This proves that with a sufficient number of mappings (4 in our case) the vehicle can be made to learn on completely unknown tracks. This has been tested on five different tracks which prove the consistency and robustness of our approach. Also the whole system works in real time which proves its efficiency.

Figure 4. The important regions from Figure 2 zoomed for clarity. (i) is the left red region, (ii) is the right red region, (iii) is the left green region, and (iv) is the right green region,

TABLE I. ACCEPTED MAPPINGS IN DIFFERENT EXPERIMENTS.

Expt. No.	First accepted (a1,a2) pair	Second accepted (a1,a2) pair	Third accepted (a1,a2) pair	Fourth accepted (a1,a2) pair
1.	-1.11, 1.23	-0.68, 0.46	-0.68, 0.46	-0.82, 0.54
2.	-1.46, 1.00	-1.31, 1.35	-1.32, 1.30	-1.32, 1.30
3.	-1.04, 1.75	-1.20, 1.48	-1.42, 1.36	-1.73, 1.35
4.	-1.73, 1.35	-0.30, 1.43	-0.63, 1.38	-0.63, 1.38
5.	-0.24, -0.11	-0.24, -0.11	-0.16, 1.13	-0.56, 1.10

TABLE II. ERROR VALUES IN DIFFERENT EXPERIMENTS

Expt. No.	Error during learning phase	Error after first accepted mapping	Error after second accepted mapping	Error after third accepted mapping	Error after fourth accepted mapping
1.	307.5	25.80	35.70	35.70	26.06
2.	412.6	44.30	19.56	14.58	18.50
3.	323.6	53.20	40.10	32.30	27.30
4.	285.3	116.50	54.80	38.00	17.02
5.	385.3	91.70	94.30	66.80	38.50

Figure 5. Graph of the learning error decreases with the number of mappings.

VI. FUTURE WORKS

In this work we are controlling the vehicle to move in any environment on the lane without considering the effect of other vehicles. However it can be made to move on a specified trajectory by carefully choosing the error function. Using the specified trajectory from say another approach of obstacle avoidance the vehicle can be moved in any sort of traffic and in any environment. This would require analyzing more scenes in the videos increasing the complexity of algorithm both in terms of time and space which are key factors in real time mapping.

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